

1 **Stakeholder Perspectives on Adolescent Sexual and**
2 **Reproductive Health Service Utilisation in Uganda’s Busoga**
3 **Region: A Qualitative Exploratory Study**

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9 **Abstract**

10 **Objective** To explore adolescents’ attitudes, perceptions, and preferences regarding sexual and
11 reproductive health (SRH) services in Busoga, Uganda, and to examine community leaders’ and
12 health providers’ perspectives to inform youth-friendly interventions.

13 **Design** Exploratory qualitative study under a constructivist paradigm, using key informant
14 interviews (KIIs) and focus group discussions (FGDs). Analysis was inductive, following Braun
15 and Clarke’s six-step thematic approach, and guided by the Health Belief Model and Andersen’s
16 Behavioural Model.

17 **Setting** Rural and urban sites in Iganga and Bugweri districts, Uganda.

18 **Participants** Six KIIs with community leaders and six with health providers; four FGDs with
19 adolescents (n=39).

20 **Results** Five themes emerged: (1) positive attitudes toward SRH but persistent misconceptions;

21 (2) structural and interpersonal barriers including distance, cost, and judgemental providers; (3)
22 preference for free, peer-led, school/community-based services with gender-matched staff; (4)
23 sociocultural constraints such as early marriage and religious prohibitions; and (5) system gaps
24 including commodity shortages and limited staff training.

25 **Conclusion** Adolescents are motivated to protect their SRH but face multilevel barriers.
26 Culturally sensitive, adolescent-friendly strategies, peer engagement, and reliable supply chains
27 are urgently needed.

28 **Keywords** Adolescent; Reproductive Health; Uganda; Qualitative Research; Health Services
29 Accessibility

30 **Key questions**

31 **What is already known on this topic**

- 32 • Adolescents in sub-Saharan Africa face stigma, cost, and distance barriers to SRH
33 services.

34 **What this study adds**

- 35 • Adolescents in Busoga prefer free, peer-led, school/community-based services and
36 describe persistent myths about contraception.

37 **How this study might affect research, practice, or policy**

- 38 • Multi-stakeholder partnerships, including faith and cultural leaders, are essential for
39 adolescent-friendly SRH policy and programming.

40 **Introduction**

41 Adolescence (10–19 years) is a critical period for establishing sexual and reproductive health
42 (SRH) behaviours that influence lifelong wellbeing and fertility outcomes.^{1 2} Globally,
43 adolescents, especially in low- and middle-income countries (LMICs) continue to face major
44 SRH challenges, including high rates of unintended pregnancy and sexually transmitted
45 infections (STIs). In sub-Saharan Africa (SSA), structural barriers such as stigma,
46 misconceptions, and limited access contribute to low utilisation of SRH care, and persistently
47 high rates of teenage pregnancy and HIV.^{3 4} Kenyan and Ethiopian studies, for example,
48 highlight transport costs, judgmental providers, and restrictive cultural norms as key barriers.^{5–8}
49 Uganda’s adolescent pregnancy rate is 24%, HIV prevalence among 15–19-year-olds is 2.1%,
50 and modern contraceptive use is only 15%.⁹ The Busoga Region is particularly affected because
51 of poverty, early marriage norms, and limited services.^{10 11} Despite national adolescent health
52 guidelines,¹² utilisation remains low due to stigma, lack of privacy, and misinformation,^{13–15} yet
53 little is known about how multiple stakeholders, including adolescents, community leaders, and
54 health providers, perceive these barriers and potential solutions. This gap limits the design of
55 locally responsive, youth-friendly interventions.

56 This study sought to address three questions:

- 57 1. What are adolescents’ attitudes, perceptions, and preferences regarding SRH services in
58 Busoga?
- 59 2. How do community leaders and health providers view adolescent SRH service needs and
60 use?

61 3. What multilevel barriers and facilitators can inform youth-friendly interventions?

62 The study was guided by the Health Belief Model ¹⁶ and Andersen’s Behavioural Model, ¹⁷ to
63 understand how individual perceptions, enabling factors, and sociocultural contexts shape SRH
64 service utilisation.

65 **Methods**

66 **Design and setting**

67 Adopted an exploratory qualitative design informed by an interpretivist paradigm to capture
68 diverse stakeholder meanings and experiences. The study was conducted in November 2024 at
69 six rural (Namirali, Kiwerere, Bulubandi, Naitandu B, Bunalwenyi C, Makandwa) and six urban
70 (Kasokoso Central II/III, Nakavule Main, Busesa, Butende, Kagamba) sites in Iganga and
71 Bugweri districts. The two districts were selected because they reflect contrasting health system
72 contexts: Bugweri has limited resources and fragile health infrastructure, whereas Iganga is
73 better resourced with stronger systems and staffing, ensuring representation of diverse conditions
74 influencing adolescent SRH service access and utilisation in the region.

75 **Participants and sampling**

76 Two participant groups were included: key community informants and adolescents.

- 77 • **Key informant interviews (KIIs):** Twelve participants were purposively selected,
78 comprising six community leaders (three cultural and three religious) and six health
79 providers drawn from health centres II to IV and the district hospital.

80 • **Focus group discussions (FGDs):** Four groups of adolescents were recruited through
81 convenience sampling. Two groups were girls aged 13 to 17 years, and two groups were
82 boys aged 17 to 19 years, with one rural and one urban group for each gender, giving a
83 total of 39 participants.

84 Sample size was determined a priori based on established guidelines,¹⁸ with data saturation
85 confirmed after 12 KIIs and four FGDs. Inclusion criteria were adolescents aged 13–19 years
86 residing in the study areas and leaders/providers identified by their communities or workplaces
87 as knowledgeable about adolescent SRH services.

88 **Data collection**

89 Semi-structured guides were pilot tested among similar but non-study localities. Refined tools
90 were used to explore attitudes, perceptions, preferences, and barriers. Sessions (60–90 min) were
91 conducted in Lusoga or English. Audio recordings were transcribed verbatim, checked against
92 recordings for accuracy, and stored on encrypted drives. NVivo 14 facilitated coding and
93 retrieval.

94 **Ethics**

95 Approved by Mildmay Uganda Research Ethics Committee (MUREC-2024-451) and Uganda
96 National Council for Science and Technology (SS3374ES). Written informed consent/assent was
97 obtained, with parental consent for minors, in accordance with the Declaration of Helsinki.

98 **Analysis**

99 Thematic analysis followed Braun and Clarke’s six steps.¹⁹ Two researchers coded transcripts
 100 independently using NVivo 14 (intercoder agreement 85%). Triangulation, member checking,
 101 and reflexive journaling enhanced credibility.

102 **Researcher characteristics and reflexivity**

103 The team included local health professionals and social scientists (two male, two female)
 104 experienced in adolescent SRH. Their professional backgrounds and shared language facilitated
 105 rapport but could introduce bias. We mitigated this through reflexive journaling, peer debriefing,
 106 and independent coding.

107 **Patient and public involvement**

108 No patient or public involvement in design or conduct; member checking validated findings.

109 **Results**

110 **Participant demographics**

111 **Table 1. Focus Group Discussions (FGDs) by District and Site**

FGD ID	District	Site type	Participant group	n (individuals)	Age range (years)	Mean age (SD)
FGD 1	Bugweri	Urban	Adolescent girls	9	13–17	16.0 (1.4)
FGD 2	Bugweri	Rural	Adolescent boys	10	17–19	18.0 (0.8)
FGD 3	Iganga	Rural	Adolescent girls	10	13–17	15.2 (1.1)
FGD 4	Iganga	Urban	Adolescent boys	10	18–19	18.4 (0.5)
Subtotal Bugweri (FGDs)				19	13–19	17.0 (1.3)
Subtotal Iganga (FGDs)				20	13–19	16.8 (1.2)

Total				39	13–19	16.9 (1.2)
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112 **Notes:** Adolescents recruited via 4 focus group discussions (2 girls' groups [n=20 total, 10 per
 113 group, rural/urban]; 2 boys' groups [n=19 total, one with 9 participants]). Data collected
 114 November 2024.

115 **Table 2. Key Informant Interviews (KIIs) by District and Site**

District	Site type	Participant role	n	Age range (years)	Mean age (approx.)	Experience (years)
Bugweri	Urban & Rural	Religious leaders (1 urban, 1 rural)	2	45–56	~50	10–20
	Urban & Rural	Cultural leaders (1 urban, 1 rural)	2	40–62	~51	15–30
	Urban & Rural	Health providers (1 urban, 1 rural)	2	38–45	~42	5–15
Subtotal Bugweri (KIIs)			6	38–62	—	5–30
Iganga	Urban & Rural	Religious leaders (1 urban, 1 rural)	2	40–60	~50	10–25
	Urban & Rural	Cultural leaders (1 urban, 1 rural)	2	42–60	~51	16–28
	Urban & Rural	Health providers (1 urban, 1 rural)	2	35–45	~40	8–16
Subtotal Iganga (KIIs)			6	35–60	—	8–25
Total KIIs			12	35–62	—	5–30

116 **Notes:** Community leaders and health providers were 12 individuals (purposive sampling, with 3
 117 individuals from each of the rural/urban types). Equal representation across rural (Namirali,
 118 Kiwerere, Bulubandi, Naitandu B, Bunalwenyi C, Makandwa) and urban (Kasokoso Central
 119 II/III, Nakavule Main, Busesa, Butende, Kagamba) sites in Iganga and Bugweri districts; dash
 120 (—) indicates not applicable. Data collected November 2024.

121 **Emergent themes**

122 **Positive attitudes towards prevention amid self-discovery**

123 Adolescents consistently described SRH services as essential for preventing unintended
124 pregnancies and sexually transmitted infections and for enabling future aspirations, while noting
125 limited parental guidance.

126 *'It helps us to prevent sexually transmitted infections and to plan for the future'* (girl, FGD,
127 Bugweri).

128 Key informants confirmed this preventive motivation: *'Most of them, especially girls, fear*
129 *pregnancies and boys fear illnesses like HIV, so they look for condoms and counselling'* (health
130 provider, KII, Bugweri).

131 **Misconceptions and negative beliefs**

132 Despite recognising benefits, adolescents reported widespread myths about contraception,
133 particularly fears of infertility, which discouraged service use.

134 *'Sometimes family planning methods may cause you to become barren'* (girl, FGD, Iganga).

135 Providers echoed these concerns: *'Some have other beliefs that when they go for family planning*
136 *in future, they will not get children'* (health provider, KII, Iganga).

137 **Barriers to service access: distance, privacy and provider attitudes**

138 Structural and interpersonal barriers, including long travel distances, extended waiting times and
139 judgemental provider attitudes, were commonly described.

140 *'Government health facilities are far and you can wait many hours before seeing a health*
141 *worker'* (boy, FGD, Iganga).

142 A provider highlighted similar challenges: *'Sometimes there are stockouts, and if adolescents do*
143 *not find the method they want, they may not come back'* (health provider, KII, Bugweri).

144 **Preferences for youth-friendly, community-based services**

145 Adolescents expressed strong preferences for free, confidential services provided in schools or
146 community settings, with peer involvement and gender-matched providers.

147 *‘During school holidays, services should come to the community and be led by youth because we
148 believe our peers’* (girl, FGD, Iganga).

149 Health workers endorsed this approach: *‘We need to collaborate with schools and create
150 adolescent-friendly corners so that young people can pick what they need in privacy’* (health
151 provider, KII, Iganga).

152 **Sociocultural influences and system-level factors**

153 Early marriage norms, religious restrictions and inconsistent parental involvement shaped
154 adolescents’ attitudes and access to care, while commodity shortages and limited staff training
155 constrained service delivery.

156 *‘Parents have lost interest in their children, so the children are growing themselves’* (health
157 provider, KII, Iganga).

158 A religious leader observed the dual role of faith: *‘Religion can guide good conduct, but
159 sometimes we marry off adolescents early and they miss many opportunities’* (religious leader,
160 KII, Bugweri).

161 Overall, adolescents demonstrated strong motivation to protect their sexual and reproductive
162 health but faced intersecting sociocultural and system-level barriers. These findings underscore
163 the need for integrated, youth-friendly SRH services that combine accurate information,
164 confidentiality, community engagement and reliable supplies.

165 **Discussion**

166 This qualitative study explored adolescents' and key community stakeholders' perspectives on
167 sexual and reproductive health (SRH) services in Busoga, Uganda. Five interrelated insights
168 emerged.

169 First, attitudes and beliefs revealed a paradox. Adolescents valued SRH services for preventing
170 pregnancy and sexually transmitted infections, yet persistent misconceptions, particularly fears of
171 infertility from modern contraception, discouraged use. Such myths have been widely documented
172 in Uganda and across sub-Saharan Africa and are known to reduce uptake of family planning
173 methods.^{20 21}

174 Second, perceptions of services highlighted structural and interpersonal barriers. Cost, distance
175 and negative provider attitudes, including judgemental behaviours and concerns about
176 confidentiality, limited access, especially in rural settings. These barriers reflect findings from
177 Kenya and Ethiopia, where adolescents avoid services when privacy is not assured or when they
178 expect moral scrutiny.^{5 7 22}

179 Third, service preferences were strikingly consistent. Adolescents expressed a strong desire for
180 free, integrated, peer-led, school or community-based services that offer confidentiality and social
181 engagement. Such preferences expand the World Health Organisation's adolescent-friendly
182 service standards²³ and align with evidence of successful peer education and digital outreach
183 interventions in other low and middle-income settings.^{24 25}

184 Fourth, sociocultural influences, including early marriage norms, restrictive religious teachings,
185 entrenched myths and inconsistent parental involvement, further constrained SRH service use.
186 While some religious leaders provided positive guidance, others reinforced prohibitions on

187 contraception. Engaging faith leaders and parents is therefore critical to dispel misinformation and
188 support adolescents' SRH needs.²⁶

189 Finally, provider and system factors, such as shortages of SRH commodities, limited staff training
190 and weak collaboration across sectors, impeded service delivery. Participants advocated for
191 continuous school-based sensitisation, community outreach and reliable supply chains to improve
192 service uptake.

193 **Comparison with existing evidence**

194 These findings are consistent with Ugandan research documenting provider stigma and limited
195 adolescent-friendly services.^{20 21} Regional studies from Kenya and Ethiopia similarly emphasise
196 the importance of confidentiality, affordability and respectful care in adolescent SRH use.^{5 7 22}
197 The strong preference for peer-led, recreation-integrated approaches builds on WHO adolescent-
198 friendly standards²³ and reflects the success of peer education and digital outreach programmes
199 reported in other low and middle-income settings.^{24 25}

200 Interpreted through the Health Belief Model, adolescents' high perceived benefits, such as
201 pregnancy prevention, coexist with high perceived barriers such as stigma and cost, which explains
202 their ambivalence towards service use. Andersen's Behavioural Model likewise highlights how
203 predisposing factors such as gender norms and religious teachings, enabling resources such as
204 transport and free services, and perceived need converge to shape health service utilisation.

205 **Implications for policy and practice**

206 Addressing sociocultural norms, including early marriage expectations and religious prohibitions,
207 requires sustained dialogue with parents, faith leaders and cultural authorities, supporting calls for
208 multi-stakeholder partnerships.²⁶ Policy actions should prioritise:

- 209 • Adolescent-friendly infrastructure and confidential service delivery
- 210 • Peer-led outreach integrated with schools and community programmes
- 211 • Integration of SRH with other adolescent services, such as mental health support and
- 212 recreational activities
- 213 • Strengthened supply chains and provider training to ensure non-judgmental, youth-
- 214 centred care

215 Collectively, these strategies can reduce misconceptions, overcome structural barriers and foster a
216 supportive environment for adolescents to access and use SRH services in Busoga and similar low-
217 resource settings.

218 **Strengths and limitations**

219 Methodological strengths included triangulation of data from adolescents, health providers, and
220 community leaders; and independent coding with high intercoder agreement, all of which
221 enhanced credibility and transferability. Limitations included the study’s confinement to two
222 districts within the Busoga region, self-report bias, translation from Lusoga to English, and
223 researcher positionality, as local health professionals could have influenced participant responses
224 despite mitigation strategies.

225 **Future research**

226 Implementation research is needed to test peer-led and school-based SRH interventions and to
227 evaluate digital and community-embedded strategies that could complement facility-based
228 services.

229 **Conclusion**

230 Adolescents in Busoga navigate SRH amid misconceptions, stigma, and access barriers.
231 Strengthening partnerships, dispelling myths, and allocating resources for adolescent-friendly
232 services are critical to improving utilisation.

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237 **Competing interests**

238 The authors declare no competing interests

239 **Data availability**

240 De-identified transcripts are available from the corresponding author on reasonable request and
241 ethics approval.

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